

The Dangers of Greed and Wealth: A Study of Luke 12:13-21

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Abstract

Jesus used different pedagogical methods in driving the Gospel message home to his listeners such as parables. Through these methods He wanted to modify human attitude towards wealth acquisition and management. Luke 12:13-21 addresses the problem of covetousness. It was told in response to the invitation of a younger brother for Christ to intervene in a family dispute over their inheritance. The particular dispute of these two brothers about the acquisition and management of wealth were of little concern to Christ in terms of his mission for humanity. Yet Christ through this parable provided principles that are very applicable to our contemporary society where the inordinate urge for wealth often leads people to engage in corrupt practices. This paper discusses the parable and draws contextual implications for Nigerian society.

Keywords: *parable, possession, wealth, money, corruption.*

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Introduction

Most biblical scholars consider the Gospel of Luke as “the most beautiful book in existence” (Martin, 1975) because, for one, its literary style is excellent. From his prologue, one can discern that he wrote his own version of the gospel very carefully, in an orderly fashion, and tried to be as accurate as possible. He chose his materials or sources very well and used them creatively to serve his intent. This is evident especially in the parables (Stagg, 1997). He made good use of parables to convey theology (Stagg, 1997). One of the theologies Luke emphasizes involves the Christian attitude towards wealth. Stein says, “No other books in the NT are as concerned about the Christian’s relationship to material possessions (Stein, 1992).” Not only in his gospel does Luke deal with this subject but also in Acts (see Acts 2:42-47; 4:32-5:11). Here, Luke portrays the positive results of generosity and seeking first the Kingdom of God: blessings for the individual and growth for the church (compare Joseph in Acts 4:36-37 and Ananias and Sapphira in 5:1-11; see also Acts 2:47; 6:7).

Luke 12:13-21 addresses the problem of covetousness. It was told in response to the invitation of a younger brother for Christ to intervene in a family dispute over their inheritance. The particular dispute of these two brothers about the acquisition and management of wealth were of little concern to Christ in terms of his mission for humanity. Jesus told the story to illustrate the point He made in verse 15: “Watch out! Be on your guard against all kinds of greed; a man’s life does not consist in the abundance of his possessions.”

The drive to possess everything, as demonstrated in this passage, is very noticeable in the quest for material possessions which dominates Nigerian society. This phenomenon is heightened by the assumption by many, that economic wealth is the answer to poverty and low self-esteem. For others, wealth is power and security. Therefore, the lust for wealth has led some to engage in many unwholesome practices and even the commercialization of religion and other corrupt practices such as, yahoo plus, ritual killings, kidnapping, prostitution, establishments of baby factories etc.

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This article aims to study exegetically Luke 12:13-21 in order to understand the attitude of Jesus towards wealth acquisition and management in the context Nigeria. The work concludes by bringing out relevant lessons for Christians in Nigeria.

Historical and Cultural Details of Inheritance

In the ancient Mediterranean region, sibling rivalry was typical, and inheritance would not be an uncommon source of contention (Malina, & Rohrbaugh, 1992). The Jewish law on inheritance is laid out in the Torah in Deut 21:15-17 and Num 27:1- 11; 36:7-9. According to the Torah, the firstborn son of the family is entitled to a double portion of the inheritance. The rest of the sons are to divide the remainder among themselves. If the father has no sons, the inheritance shall go to the daughters, as in the case of the daughters of Zelophehad. The inheritance shall remain within the tribe of the family and must not be transferred from tribe to tribe. Thus, the daughters of Zelophehad, in order to retain their inheritance, had to marry within the tribe of Manasseh, the tribe to which their father belonged. Ancient Jewish custom also allowed inheritance to be distributed among the heirs even if the father were still living if a son demanded it - this was the case with the prodigal son (Malina, & Rohrbaugh, 1992). Apart from his request, Luke did not give any more details about the man. Was he duped out of his inheritance? Was his proper share not given to him? Or did he want more than what he received?

The man was not really out of order in bringing the problem to Jesus because it was common in that day for people to ask religious teachers or rabbis to settle their disputes (Barclay, 1975). The reason behind this is that the law of the land was embodied in the Torah, and since Israel was a theocracy, who was in a better position to settle disputes than the authorities on the Scriptures—the rabbis (Stacy, 1997)? And Jesus, having been recognized by this time in His ministry as a rabbi or one who spoke on the Scriptures with great authority (Luke 4:32, 36; Matt 7:29), was approached by the man with his family problem.

With this in mind, it is interesting to note that Jesus refused to help the man. Why did He object to being the arbitrator? Luke did not tell us the reason. One can only surmise. Probably, though Jesus was looked up to as a rabbi, He did not immediately assume that it was proper for Him to be a judge, not having been formally recognized by the religious hierarchy as a rabbi (Plummer, 1981); or perhaps because it was not part of His mission to try to change the structure of the civil laws of Israel as embodied in the Torah. He said He came to fulfil the Law, not to abolish it (Luke 24:44; Matt 5:17). Jesus also said that He came to seek and save the lost (Luke 19:10). He did not come simply to settle civil disputes; He had a much higher calling. As Stacy asserts,

The brother in Luke 12:13 is not a poor, disaffected person whose cause Jesus can step up to champion. The dispute is about money, not persons, and Jesus seems to have very little interest in money *per se*. Jesus' belief in the Kingdom of God and the radical reorientation of life it brings was so central to his teaching that he regards disputes over furniture and dishes and silverware as irrelevant (Stacy, 1997).

The Lord saw the man's real problem. "What this individual needed was not some casuistic legal ruling by a religious teacher but a basic understanding of how possessions relate to the purpose of life (Stein, 1992)." The Lord also saw the real motive of the man. He was consumed by greed. "Greed is to be rejected, for the meaning and purpose of life is not found in the accumulation of wealth and possessions (Stein, 1992)."

Nolland offers a very good insight on the reason why the Lord refused the man's request. He says it is most likely that Jesus turned down the man's appeal because he was usurping Jesus' authority for his personal gain. In other words, he was attempting to use the status and authority of Jesus to satisfy his covetousness (Nolland, 1989), the pronouncement in verse 15 confirms this. Malina and Rohrbaugh hold that behind this verse is "the traditional peasant assumption that greed is invariably the underlying motive of anyone able to gain a surplus (Malina, & Rohrbaugh, 1992)." This is due to the fact that in ancient Palestine, the people's idea of goods is that they are limited, and have already been distributed. Therefore, if one acquired more, it meant that someone's piece of the pie got smaller. The individual enjoyed a

surplus at someone else's expense; thus, he was not being fair. "An honorable man would thus be interested only in what was rightfully his and would have no desire to gain anything more, that is, to take what was another's (Malina, & Rohrbaugh, 1992)." That is why to be rich in those days said a lot more about one's morality than one's economic status. Commonly, people thought of the rich as greedy (Malina, & Rohrbaugh, 1992).

Luke 12:13-21 within Its Larger Context

Luke 12:13-21 belongs to the travel narratives (see Luke 9:51-19:27), a literary feature peculiar to the Third Gospel. Luke here records a great deal of material which is absent in Matthew and Mark. It is in this section that Luke demonstrates vividly Jesus' extensive use of parables to teach very important lessons relating to ethics and the kingdom motif. It is set as one of Jesus' discourses while traveling to Jerusalem. Now, this is not one of Jesus' trips to Jerusalem. This is the journey that will eventually lead Him to the cross. The events narrated here, scholars say, cover the last six months of Jesus' life before being crucified. Luke tells us that Jesus "sets his face" (9:51) towards Jerusalem. Jesus was resolved to fulfill His mission. Stacy describes the mood surrounding the events as "'crunch time,' with high anxiety all around (Stacy, 1997)." Much of the content of this document is unique to Luke and/or Matthew, also known as non-Markan material.

Martin regards this section of Luke's Gospel as the most important unit because it is here that the Gospel's distinctive features come out. This section is primarily didactic, "even the parables in this section have a didactic-paraenetic flavor (Martin, 1975)." Jesus addressed the parable primarily to His disciples (Luke 12:1) but also to the swelling crowd that was following Him. In the context of chapter 12, He was teaching them how a disciple should live in the Kingdom of God. Stacy divides the discourse into three areas: persecution (vv.1-12), possessions (vv. 13-34), and the parousia (vv.35-48) (Stacy, 1997). Jesus just came from a meal in a Pharisee's house and was proceeding on His journey, giving various warnings and encouragements to His disciples, when one from the crowd asked Him to settle an inheritance dispute between him and his brother. Jesus found the request a very good springboard to teach about the right attitude towards wealth or material possessions. He told them the story of the rich fool.

The Text of Luke 12:13-21

There are no significant textual issues in the text. Therefore, the work adopts the text as it is.

Literary Structure of Luke 12:13-21

- A. The request by the Aggrieved Brother (v.13)
- B. Jesus' Answer to the Aggrieved Brother (v.14)
- C. Jesus' Exhortation to the Crowd (vv.15-20)
 - 1. The Dangers of Greed (v.15)
 - 2. The Parable of the Rich Fool (vv.16-21)

Content Analysis of Luke 12:13-21

The above structure shows that the pericope deals with the uncertainty of human life and the transient nature of material possessions. Therefore, this article would exegetically analyse the text by faithful to the structure.

Verses 13: This verse links the pericope to the preceding discourse (vv.1-12), making it part of the larger context of chapter 12. In this verse, the imperative *eipen* is used for "tell". Therefore, the man is commanding Jesus to actually order his brother to divide the inheritance with him. He did not make a request that Jesus should act as a judge; he was giving a command to the Him. It was ironic because the fact that he approached Jesus with this issue tells the readers that in a way, he respected the authority of

Jesus. However, the way he spoke to Jesus was anything but respectful. In answering the man, Jesus uses the vocative of *anthrōpos* which is *anthrōpe*. According to Fitzmyer, “it is a rebuking term, implying aloofness (Fitzmyer, 1981).”

The ancient Jewish legal system left no doubt concerning the dividing of family inheritance. It provided for the first son to succeed the father as the head of the home and guaranteed him the inheritance of a double portion of his father’s estate, leaving the remaining son(s) to share the final one-third (Deut 21:17; 1 Chron 5:1-2) (Horn, 1979). Where there is no male family member, the family’s wealth passes on to the daughters on the condition that they marry within their tribe (Num 27:1-11; 36:6-9). The cause of the younger brother’s contention over family inheritance in the passage in question is not obvious. Some suggestions have been made in the quest to understand this situation. First, the elder brother might have taken beyond what the legal system authorizes. Second, the complainant might be challenging the law because he felt unprotected. Lastly, it is suggested that the elder brother might have desired a partnership in the management of the inheritance; an option unacceptable to the complainant. While the last option might have been unwelcome by the plaintiff, in the ancient world families could jointly hold their property and share its resources for business purposes (Bock, 1994). This, however, would still be at the supervision of the elder brother. Thus, the complaint of the youngest in this setting could have arisen from his protest against the elder brother’s legitimate share or his (the complainant) disapproval of the established legal rights governing the management of inheritance which may have left him with less than what he desired.

Verse 14: Jesus’ Response to the Complainant (the brother)

The aggrieved brother calls Jesus “rabbi,” a term used to refer to religious teachers who are supposed to have authority to teach and abdicate on ethical matters such as the one in question. This title is generously applied to Christ in the Gospels (see Matt 26:25; Mark 14:45; John 1:38, 49; 3:2, 26; 4:31; 6:25; 9:2; 11:8). The title was used for scholars and teachers of the law. It is assumed that their learning and knowledge of the Torah and their interpretation of the religious duties prescribed in it are infallible and thus unquestionable (Horn, 1979). During the time of Christ it was not unusual for these honored teachers to travel from one place to another, dispensing answers to social and ethical concerns. Therefore, it was with this notion that the aggrieved brother approached Christ with the request to intervene in his affairs. But the expectation of the aggrieved brother is dashed with Christ’s refusal to be drawn into this family affair.

Two principal reasons have been adduced for Jesus’ refusal to accede to this request. First, Barnes suggests that Christ’s refusal was because the primary purpose of His ministry was not to settle civil affairs which the laws of the land could resolve (Barnes, 1976). The second reason raised is the question of motivation of the younger brother who had asked Jesus to intervene in this family dispute. The mood of the expression—the imperative, which in this context could be seen as a command, may point to this. The phrase communicating his request in verse 13 could read, “Teacher, command my brother to divide the inheritance with me (Bock, 1994)” implies that this position from the perspective of the complainant, recognizes certain authority in Jesus which could enable Him to issue such a command. With this understanding, the request may not have been to arbitrate, but to advocate for the petitioner against his brother. Consequently, Jesus’ response was to distance Himself from trivialities inconsistent with His divine mission to save humanity from the very wantonness plaguing the complainant.

Verse 15: Jesus’ Teaching on the Ethics of wealth/Possessions

Verse 15 is the transitional statement of the parable. Many scholars believe that this passage was not really Jesus’ own statement, but was a Lukan addition (Nolland, 1989; Fitzmyer, 1981). Nevertheless, one can say that this is Jesus’ main point in the parable. Knowing the man’s real motive, Jesus warns the disciples and the multitudes against greed. He reinforces this by saying that it does not follow that if one has an abundance of goods, one’s life is secure, and that he or she will enjoy a meaningful and fulfilling life. The statement is very profound and it is quite difficult to understand at first. That is why the parable was given.

Caveat on the Dangers of Greed and Wealth

Rather than consenting to the request of the petitioner, Jesus takes advantage of the opportunity to warn of the dangers of greed or covetousness. But this time, He speaks to the crowd (*autous*, “them”) who is His first audience. In warning about greed, Jesus employs the Greek term *pleonexía*, a word which can be translated as “greediness”, “avarice”, “covetousness.” In a non-biblical sense, *pleonexía* could be used positively as in Epictetus 2, 10:9. In this context it could denote a desire for more knowledge or holiness. But it is suggested that its scriptural usage is always negative (Perry, 1975). Thus in the context of usage, *pleonexía*, could refer to the gross selfishness and inordinate desire to have more by denying others what is legitimately theirs. While Luke does not elucidate on this theme of greed—mentioning it only in 8:14 and 16:14, its dangers are frequently mentioned in other passages of the New Testament (Rom 1:29; 2 Cor 9:5; Col 3:5; Eph 4:19; 5:3; 2 Pet 2:3-14). Speaking of the possessive nature of greed, Plutarch observed that “greed never rests from the acquiring of more.” It drives its captives to an insatiable state where everything that matters is wealth, no matter how it comes (Johnson, 1991).

Next, Christ admonishes that life is not measured by possessions (v.15b). Certain difficulties attend the clear intention of Jesus in this part. Perhaps, it is because of this line that some have suggested Luke 12:13-15 is the work of an editor. But in our view this line is entirely appropriate, and there is no reason that it should be labeled secondary. The warning against covetousness provides the perfect backdrop for the parable.

The Greek word, *ζωή*, translated “life” in v. 15, could be symbolic and may thus mean “happiness,” or “quality of living.” It could also be taken literally as the “physical life.” If understood from the first two meanings (happiness and quality of life), Christ could here be saying: “Happiness in life is not determined by the amount of wealth one has at his possession, even if the quality of life might be enhanced by items of luxury and comfort.” On the other hand, if the “life” here is physical, he could be saying: “wealth does not guarantee the length of life; it cannot prolong it.” Earlier in His teachings on the Mount, Christ had stated that no person could lengthen his life by worries for wealth and the cares of life. In this vein therefore, the latter meaning of life as physical in v. 15, seems more consistent with the passage as is illustrated by the parable of the rich but foolish farmer who follows this warning.

Christ’s injunction elevates the meaning and value of life above riches and wealth. Security of life is not in amassing property. This was a radical challenge to the original hearers and also to contemporary society’s measure of success. The message is clear; possessions do not guarantee comfort and security, nor lengthen one’s life, thus, one is not to be obsessed by it.

The Parable of the Rich Fool (verses 16-21)

These introductory warnings concerning the dangers of greed prepare the stage for the parable of the rich but idiotic man told in verses 16-21. This parable is the fitting illustration of the statement of Christ in verse 15b about the uncertainty of human life and the transient nature of wealth. The parable does not suggest that the man had acquired the wealth illegally or coveted it. Yet it plainly shows that obsession with wealth, whether acquired genuinely or through dubious means, is a vain pursuit.

The man in question could have been a wealthy Jewish farmer who, beyond his careful planning and forecast, had excess returns in his harvest for the year in question. In such a situation he could be spared the worries of life (v. 19). In handling this abundance, his human wisdom was displayed in his decision to expand his barns to accommodate the bounty harvest. Being a farmer, the barns certainly would be for the storage of the grains, possibly wheat and barley, two very important grains in Palestine. This type of barn was “commonly made by the ancients, underground, where grain could be kept a long time more-safe (sic) from thieves and from vermin (Barnes, 1976).” In fact, no wise farmer or investor could think and do less than the man in this parable sought to do. Jesus had no query on the manner of the abundance, since there was no indication of Him being a stern farmer such as indicated in James 5:4.

What then was the basis of His rebuke as *aphrōn*—foolish or senseless (verse 20), a person “who rejects the knowledge and precepts of God as the basis for life.” Barclay offers a further insight thus:

There is no (other) parable which is so full of the words, I, me, my and mine....The rich fool was aggressively self-centered...When this man had superfluity of goods, the one thing that never entered his mind was to give any away. His whole attitude was the very reverse of Christianity. Instead of denying himself, he aggressively affirmed himself; Instead of finding his happiness in giving, he tried to conserve it by Keeping (Barclay, 1975).

Commenting further on the attitude of the rich fool, Geldenhuys also observes:

He considered that he had the full command over his life and over all his possessions and thus spoke about 'my barns, my fruits, my goods, and my soul' (vv. 18, 19).He did not regard the possessions as things lent to him by God's grace and to be used for his own pleasure and enjoyments (Geldenhuys, 1951).

In the light of the disposition of the rich fool, God addresses the man on his own pragmatic terms of not dealing with kingdom matters or life beyond the present realm, but on the question of mundane affairs—his possessions. Thus, he has to leave it all, possibly to an incompetent heir or to no one in particular (see Eccl 2:18-19).

Verse 21 is the application meant to strengthen the point Jesus made in verse 15. Indeed, if people will try to find life, hope and security in things or wealth, they will be disappointed. They will reap pain, suffering, and even destruction.

Finally, therefore Luke 12:13-21 leaves one with the following insights:

- i. Selfishness involves the urge to have more at the expense of what legitimately belongs to others and it brings dissatisfaction with what one has.
- ii. Greed is possessive and leads to destruction.
- iii. Obsession with wealth, whether acquired legitimately or otherwise is contrary to the God's will for humankind.
- iv. Happiness in life is not measured by the amount of a person's earthly possessions nor can an extension to a person's life be guaranteed by one's wealth.
- v. Life has to be lived in the light of eschatological realities, since whatever a person has on earth would be ultimately left following death.

Nigerian Society and Material Possessions

The quest for material possessions by most Christians in Nigeria is mostly motivated by fear and selfishness. Many Christians seek to accumulate wealth and possessions because they fear that they might not have enough to live on and to live comfortably till the end of their days. They are always fearful of suffering, hunger and the lack of comforts in life. So it is natural for them to grow their wealth and their assets so that they can provide for the needs of their family and loved ones, and especially in their old age.

The Nigerian society has been hyped with the quest for material possessions, thereby making so many to think that life consists in abundance of possessions. George Hubbard's perspective of the message of the Parable of the Rich Fool speaks powerfully. He asks this question: what made the rich man a fool in God's eyes? Or why did God call him a fool? If we look at him using today's modern standards, we could call him a practical man. After all, he worked hard; he did not gain his wealth through illegal or immoral means. In fact, his farm provided jobs for others. And he was wise to save for his future. Yet, he was a fool before God. This is because he wisely provides for his body but not for his soul. Hubbard puts it so simply yet effectively:

He was wise to secure himself against material want for the time which would probably be his. There was no folly in this. There was every probability that he would live for many years, and he was wise to prepare

for that. But while that was only a probability, there was the positive certainty that his soul would live through all eternity, and he was a thrifless fool to make no provision for that... Wise to foresee and supply the needs of the body; fool to imagine that the soul can be fed with corn and wheat (Hubbard, 1907).

The falsehood that security can be found in covetous wealth accumulation has led some Christians in public offices to engage in severe corrupt practices to amass for themselves a greater percentage of wealth. It is sad, however, that most of the perpetrators boldly defend their action and explain them away. At the same time, basic amenities such as water, light, good roads, affordable health care and other social benefits for the masses are conspicuously absent. The unequal distribution of wealth has left no less than seventy percent of the populace below the poverty line.

In the circumstances described above, one may ask: "what is the relevance of Luke 12:13-21 for Christians in Nigeria today?" One can say that that the text speaks to the individual wealthy Nigerian Christians whose manner of wealth acquisitions is questionable and whose security is wealth. Second, it speaks to the country of Nigeria collectively, which in the midst of abundant resources has a high level of its populace living in penury.

The Relevance of Luke 12:13-21 for Christians in Nigeria

In Nigeria today, it is very easy to get caught up in the race for more and more things. People think that there is life in the acquisition of wealth because it provides security, hope and fulfilment. But what is life? Is it the life here on earth or is it the life beyond? Jesus says eternal life is knowing God (John 10:10); security is in giving (Prov 11:24); and true hope and fulfilment are in God (Jer 17:7-8; Ps 146; 1 Chron 4:10; Eph 3:17-19). Jesus says, "If anyone would come after me, he must deny himself and take up his cross and follow me. For whoever wants to save his life will lose it, but whoever loses his life for me will find it. What will it profit a man if he gains the whole world, loses his life?" (see Matt 16:24-26; Mark 8:34-36; Luke 9:23-25).

Luke 12:13-21 does not suggest that possessions in themselves are evil. Rather the query is on the obsession for possessions and its management. Since possessions and wealth do not define the ultimate purpose of life now and even at the eschaton, Jesus admonishes that a person with eschatological orientation would moderate his quest for wealth and consider such bestowals as the beginning of responsibilities (Nolland, 1993) because even honest wealth requires faithful stewardship which includes being rich towards God and impacts on one's view of eternal realities. Coming to terms with this fact can moderate the obsession to wealth acquisition and management by Christians in Nigeria. Consequently, this could engender generosity rather than self-centeredness--the challenge that the rich fool could not overcome.

This parable also teaches Christians in Nigeria about the function of wealth or possessions in our life: they are not only for us, not for our benefit alone; our wealth and possessions are meant for others as well (1 Chron 29:3-4; Matt 6:1-4; 19:21; Acts 2:45; 4:32-36; 11:29). We work hard not because we want to enrich ourselves with material things but to provide for the needs of those who depend on us: our families and loved ones; other people--the needy, the under-privileged, the disabled, and the poor in our society. God wills that we help these kinds of people with our resources, even financial resources (see Mark 10:17-31).

Jesus challenges Christians in Nigeria to have a heavenly perspective of life here on earth. Indeed, true disciples of Jesus Christ understand that the lives they live here have eternal repercussions. They do not live for this life only but also for the life beyond death, which is what really matters the most. They understand that they are just pilgrims here on earth. Their real home and treasures are in heaven not in this world.

Wealth does not guarantee the extension of life nor does its possession secure eternal life. For instance, the rich fool never imagined his life was coming to an end suddenly. Hence, death to him was not

imminent. But at the very moment of abundance when he concluded plans on how to satiate himself, death came knocking. Thus, to “define life in terms of things is the ultimate reversal of the creature serving the creation and ignoring the Creator (Bock, 1994).” While needs should be met and satisfied, it is necessary to always note that any possession and wealth more than human need is superfluous (Malherbe, 1996).

Conclusion

Luke 12:13-21 shows that God does not principally loath wealth. But He abhors covetousness and greed, which compel one to secure wealth at all cost. He also disdains wealth management that neglects the needy and other appropriate use of wealth and possession in society. Thus, since wealth is no substitute for goodness and character and is not a guarantee for the real essence of life accountability towards God rather than the desire to satisfy ephemeral needs should govern the pursuit of and management of wealth and possession.

Life does not consist in how much one has. It is not living a luxurious life but when one is able to give oneself to others. When Christians share what they have with others, whether resources, talents, wealth and possessions, they are enriched by the friendship, love and bond they establish with others. In giving, Christians receive. Love is the greatest of riches and possessions Christians can have in their lives because no one can take away from them. Jesus said, “Do not store up for yourselves treasures on earth, where moth and rust consume and where thieves break in and steal; but store up for yourselves treasures in heaven, where neither moth nor rust consumes and where thieves do not break in and steal. For where your treasure is, there your heart will be also” (see Matt 6:19-21).

The divine pronouncement on the rich but foolish farmer, constitute an invitation to the readers of Luke to evaluate their attitude towards possession and management in view of eschatology. The conclusion of this illustrative parable counsels that life has to be lived in the light of eschatological orientation.

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